

CONCEPTION OF HAPPINESS IN “A COUNTERINTUITIVE APPROACH TO LIVING A GOOD LIFE” BY MARK MANSON

Samigjonova Mokhira

Bachelor's, Student

National University of Uzbekistan,

samigjonovamokhira@gmail.com

+998 97 1356886

Annotation. This paper examines the idea of conventional happiness, moreover, the role of being oblivious to failures on the way to achieve success, has been analyzed from the literary point of view

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada an'anaviy baxt g'oyasi, shuningdek, muvaffaqiyat yo'lidagi qiyinchiliklarga taslim bo'lmaslik yo'llari, adabiy tomondan tahlil qilingan

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается идея общепринятого счастья, кроме того, важность преодоления неудач на пути к достижению успеха, рассмотрены с литературной точки зрения

Key words: conception, happiness, positive, negative, failure, life, person, experience, achievement, social media

Kalit so'zlar: tushuncha, baxt, ijobiy, salbiy, muvaffaqiyatsizlik, hayot, inson, tajriba, yutuq, ijtimoiy tarmoq

Ключевые слова: понятие, счастье, позитивный, негативный, неудача, жизнь, человек, опыт, достижение, социальная сеть

Over the past few years the “How to be happy” advertisement by psychologists and bloggers have been shared on social media probably a million times. The aim of this paper is to distinguish the conception of happiness interrelated with Mark Manson’s book. While analyzing Mark Manson’s book and its inner fields, his own history must be taken into consideration. He is 38 years old. Before he was a writer, he had been a failed musician who grew up in Austin, Texas and moved to Boston to attend university. He graduated from Boston University in 2007 with a degree in International Relations and Business. His life’s mission is to improve the public conversation around personal development and happiness. He also aims to share this information as widely as possible and as inexpensively as possible - as he believes mental health and self-improvement are not something for the few or the privileged, but rather they should be a right for anyone who has taken on the responsibility to improve themselves.

Happiness is something that people seek to find, yet what defines happiness can vary from one person to the next. When most people talk about the true meaning of happiness, they might be talking about how they feel in the present moment or referring to a more general sense of how they feel about life overall. Because happiness tends to be such a broadly defined term, psychologists and other social scientists typically use the term subjective well-being when they talk about this emotional state. Just as it sounds, subjective well-being tends to focus on an individual's overall personal feelings about their life in the present. Two key components of happiness (or subjective well-being) are:

- **The balance of emotions:** Everyone experiences both positive and negative emotions, feelings, and moods. Happiness is generally linked to experiencing more positive feelings than negative ones.
- **Life satisfaction:** This relates to how satisfied you feel with different areas of your life including your relationships, work, achievements, and other things

that you consider important. Another definition of happiness comes from the ancient philosopher Aristotle, who suggested that happiness is the one human desire, and all other human desires exist as a way to obtain happiness. He believed that there were four levels of happiness: happiness from immediate gratification, from comparison and achievement, from making positive contributions, and from achieving fulfillment.

But what about unhappiness? Unhappiness - or sadness - is a part of life. Everyone experiences unhappiness once in a while. But what if it seems like you're unhappy all of the time? What causes your unhappiness? Research seems to show that unhappiness - and happiness - is caused by patterns in our lives: patterns in the things we *do*, which are called behavioral patterns, and patterns in the things we *think*, which are called cognitive patterns. Different behavioral and cognitive patterns lead to different emotional patterns, which are part of what determines how happy we feel from day to day. The path to being happier can be long, and sometimes requires great changes in one's life. In fact, being happy is something you need to cultivate every day, but adopting the right patterns in your life and then sticking to them. We all feel down from time to time – and if it's in response to a particular situation, that's normal. However, many people feel unhappy *much* of the time, and that points to a bigger problem. So what are the main causes of unhappiness? Why is everyone so unhappy? And more importantly, what can you do if you often feel unhappy? Mark Manson wrote “The desire for a more positive experience is itself a negative experience. And paradoxically, the acceptance of one's negative experience is itself a positive experience.” [“A counterintuitive approach to living a good life”, 2016: p.13].

Being oblivious. You probably think it means living indifferent to everything. But this would only mean that you are rude, insensitive, careless, and many other unpleasant things. It means you are showing a huge lack of feelings —

which would finally issue from a lack of empathy. Mark goes further here, labeling that someone as a psycho. A psycho shows a lack of care and sensitivity when in reality, they live by fear. They are insensitive for fearing life; they care a lot about being indifferent and about the opinion of others. So they are not genuinely indifferent, but they show themselves impervious to the feeling because they are too afraid to leave their cave and face responsibility. But this book is more profound than this simple explanation and deserves a better analysis. We gathered 4 crucial ideas that we want to share with the audience.

Lesson 1— Suffering is essential to your growth: The book teaches us how suffering is inevitable, the light it's accepting that without that suffering, growth is not possible. Mark Manson explains how only through discomfort, suffering, and pain can you grow. This happens because the only discomfort will lead to seeking change. He writes: *"We suffer for the simple reason that suffering is biologically useful. It is nature's preferred agent for inspiring change"*. **Pain will inspire change because it brings discomfort, and when you feel uncomfortable, you'll seek comfort, so, ultimately, you are seeking change.** So next time you're feeling some form of pain, instead of seeing it as a bad thing and trying to get away from it, accept it, allow yourself to feel it, and be reassured that it exists for a valid reason. If you do this, you'll not only experience the pain becoming weaker, but you'll also become more used to it. You'll eventually be "happy" for its presence in your life.

Lessons 2— You are not different: This lesson is of paramount importance — wouldn't it be the case of people constantly feeling some entitlement. During your life, you may be led to believe that you're exceptional in some way, either by feeling that you're better than everyone else or by feeling that you're a victim and everything is against you. **Truthful news: you're not exceptional; you're not different in any way. You have your problems to deal with, just like anyone**

else. It may happen that one or two people reading this story will be among the exceptional undermost amount of the population. Even if that's the case, these people are not successful by the amount of positivism their self-esteem is created. When your self-esteem is at a high or low, you're just being "entitled" — like Mark Manson likes to call — meaning that you're just entitling yourself to be different in any aspect of your life. The self-confidence you show is just a delusion. **And why can't entitlement work?** Because with entitlement, you'll need to feel good about yourself all the time, which will be an obstruction to accepting your problems when you should be dealing with them instead. In reality, your true self-worth is measured by how you choose to feel about the negative aspects of your life. If you think that you should be extraordinary, then everyone has the right to assume the same. But if everyone were to be exceptional, the concept would immediately cease to exist. Extraordinariness only exists amongst mediocrity.

Lesson 3— You are 100% responsible for your life events: Yes, 100%, you read right! Ultimately, we are responsible for our choices, and that determines how you choose your values and how you choose to react to certain situations. It's all about accepting responsibility for your life. It's about assuming that you own your life, choosing to be responsible for it, in the end, also choosing to be accountable for your problems. This is a crucial step in solving problems. As soon as you understand this, you'll stop avoiding your responsibility and act upon your problems; because they're yours! They don't just appear and disappear out of thin air. This concept of responsibility is important, but it's also essential not to confuse responsibility with fault. Even though these may sometimes be used together, they're different. *"Imagine you are walking on the sidewalk, and you are hit by a car. It's probably not your fault that you were hit by the car, but it's still your responsibility because you chose to walk on that sidewalk at that time of the day. If*

that doesn't convince you, you're still left with one responsibility — the one to choose how you'll react to that situation. Now picture a case where you decided to jump to the middle of a road and get hit by a car. Here you have both the responsibility and the fault for that action. [“A counterintuitive approach to living a good life”, 2016: p.96].”So you can be either responsible and have the fault, or don't be guilty but still responsible. **Ultimately we choose our problems by choosing how we react to them.** It's also by choice that your values and metrics are created. You have the freedom to choose your values and the metrics you use to measure them. Thus understanding this possibility of choosing everything that succeeds in your life, you also have the power in your hands. This power is the first weapon for correctly dealing with all your problems.

Lesson 4— You can, should, and will be wrong: People usually don't like to be wrong, but if you look back in time, you'll find out that most of the individual and collective certainties that existed were later found wrong. For their time, groups of people could have believed they reached some universal truth, but even then, not everyone believed in that universal truth. And since we, humans, can remember, we have evolved as different ideas came to birth and died. The first thing here is that you will always be wrong in everything you do and believe in. Of course, you can be more or less wrong, but nothing will ever be entirely true. You need to experience things to find them, knowing that even experience will be wrong somehow. **Nothing is perfect; nothing is absolute. You will be wrong.** And with this in mind, you probably already understood that there is no growth without error. We evolved through multiple mistakes. You must accept that being wrong is part of life. It's okay to be wrong, and “you can” be because if you feel you can't, then you're only narrow-minded. And that's the number-one condition to keep living your shitty values. Suffering is inevitable, and you must accept it. If you accept it to be part of your growth, you'll also accept failing, and

you'll end up doing things that you were afraid of at the beginning. It can be hard at first, but with time it gets easier, and it will make you happier in the long term.

From a literary point of view, "A COUNTERINTUITIVE APPROACH TO LIVING A GOOD LIFE" argues that individuals should seek to find meaning through what they find to be important and only engage in values that they can control. Everything worthwhile in life is won through surmounting the associated negative experience. If you are able to be oblivious to the pain your goals require, then you become unstoppable. The moments when we don't give up and take action are often the moments that most define the course of our lives.

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